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**Characteristics and Operating Analysis of Halide
Perovskites-based Memristor with Light Stimulation**

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Abstract

Halide-perovskite memristors combine mixed ionic–electronic transport (MIEC) with a rich optical response which is significantly tuneable by electrical and optical stimuli. This thesis provides an in-depth characterization and modelling of (FTO | PEDOT:PSS | MAPbBr₃ | Au) memristive devices which show on off ratio of more than 20 and endurance of more than 150 cycles. We follow the transition from capacitive to inductive hysteresis using Impedance Spectroscopy (IS) and Current- Voltage (IV) characteristics, the extract voltage-dependent relaxation time $\tau_k(u)$, and validate the Conductance-Activated quasi-Linear Memristor (CALM) model. By combining DC I–V hysteresis loops, IS Nyquist analysis, and pulse-train potentiation/depression under dark and 530 nm illumination, the thesis builds a benchmark report for halide perovskite memristors for further investigations related to neuromorphic devices, photo memory, etc for both experimental and computational work.

Dedication: This work is dedicated to Late Prof Santosh Kumar, an educator, mentor and a superstar professor.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation

Modern artificial intelligence workloads are running up against the so-called memory wall¹: energy and latency problems arise as data must do a back and forth between physically separate logic and memory units in von Neumann processors. Neuromorphic hardware tackles this inefficiency by allowing in-memory computing^{2,3}. Memristors are two terminal devices which possess hysteresis in their I-V characteristics and are promising due to large memory window, excellent memory density, wide tunability.⁴ However, this interest is yet to translate into a good collective understanding of the working principle of these devices. Several studies have been done in this area previously, however, they usually focus on few specific characterisation techniques to comment on the physics. This creates a significant void in literature dealing with experimentally informed models to study these devices. Furthermore, photo synaptic memristive devices have seen a sudden rise in interest as well³, although not many reports have come to our attention with halide perovskite memristors dealing with both optical and electrical stimulus. In principle, long exciton diffusion length and excellent absorption coefficient make these devices an excellent candidate for the same. Thus, we wish to investigate regarding said aspects of the memristor with both electrical and optical stimulus using I-V characteristics, impedance spectroscopy, chronoamperometry and numerical modelling. Importantly we would like to emphasise on the applicability of current available models for the memristors simulating I-V characteristics and pulse train potentiation as well as comment on possible improvements.

1.2. Metal Halide Perovskites Memristors

Metal halide perovskites (general formula ABX_3 , where A = organic/inorganic cation, B = divalent metal, X = halide) have transformed photovoltaics due to low temperature solution processing, high absorption coefficient and low cost⁵. The same lattice also hosts mobile ionic species—most notably halide vacancies. Under an external electric field these ions redistribute, modulating interfacial band bending and thereby the electronic conductance in a smooth, analogue fashion. Such mixed ionic electronic conduction (MIEC) produces interesting hysteresis I-V characteristics⁶, ranging from capacitor like clockwise loops to inductor like counterclockwise loops as the bias is swept. Being simple devices, memristors are good platform to study charge transport mechanisms.

1.3. Neuromorphic Functionality

A neuromorphic “synapse” must implement both potentiation (incremental conductance increase) and depression (incremental decrease) in response to millisecond scale voltage spikes. The volatile branch of perovskite memristors—where ionic relaxation times are long enough for short term plasticity but finite enough for self-reset is similar to biological short term memory functions such as paired pulse facilitation (PPF)⁷ Furthermore, the wide optical absorption band of $MAPbBr_3$ introduces an additional photo stimulus moderate green light generates free carriers that screen internal fields, accelerate ion motion, and thus tune the device time constants by up to an order of magnitude. Light therefore provides an external control and stimulus for adapting learning rates in hybrid optoelectronic neural networks.

1.4. Objectives

The objective is to quantify and model the dynamic behaviour of volatile MAPbBr₃ memristors operated under combined electrical and optical stimuli. Specific objectives are as follows:

- (O1) Lab training and fabricate FTO | PEDOT:PSS | MAPbBr₃ | Au devices with reproducible morphology and contact quality.
- (O2) Systematically characterise DC I–V hysteresis as a function of scan rate (0.5–10 V s⁻¹) in dark and under 530 nm illumination.
- (O3) Extract bias resolved ionic relaxation times $\tau_{\text{exp}}(u)$ from Electro Impedance Spectroscopy (100 kHz – 100 mHz) using a minimal R_s–C_m–R_X–L_X equivalent circuit.
- (O4) Implement the Conductance Activated quasi–Linear Memristor (CALM) model, parameterised by the experimental $\tau_{\text{exp}}(u)$, and validate it against pulse train potentiation.
- (O5) Thesis preparation and submission

Figure 1: Gantt chart for the TFM

1.5. Outline

Chapter 2 surveys the state of the art, perovskite memristors, capacitive versus inductive hysteresis, impedance analysis, the CALM framework, and light effects.

Chapter 3 details the fabrication process, electrical/optical measurement setups, and data analysis.

Chapter 4 presents the experimental results alongside CALM simulations.

Chapters 5 and 6 discuss resource budgeting and environmental considerations.

Chapter 7 conclusion.

2. State of the art of the technology used or applied in this thesis

2.1. Metal Halide Perovskites

Metal halide perovskites are a class of crystalline materials following the structure ABX_3 , where A is a Cation, B is a metal anion (typically Pb) and X is a halogen, thus for the material we focused on in this work, A is methyl ammonium (MA), B is lead (Pb) and X is Br, giving $MAPbBr_3$. These materials exhibit excellent charge transport properties, tunability and ease of fabrication, usually can be solution processed into a thin film. This allows halide perovskites to be excellent candidates for their use in various areas including energy harvesting, light emission, memory storage, neuromorphic computing, etc.

Figure 2: illustration of a Metal Halide Perovskite crystal lattice (image ref: InfoMat. 2019;1:430–459)

2.2. Memristors

With the advent of big data, AI and in general the impending failure of Moore's law, the research community has shown increased interest in memristors for their data storage and in-memory computing needs. The memristor was first devised by Leon Chua⁸ as the missing fourth element of electrical circuits exhibiting hysteresis in its I-V characteristics. This hysteresis essentially means that the current has two values for a voltage, and the instantaneous value depends upon its history. Like other phenomenon with hysteresis for example magnetization used in mechanical hard disks, memory is a natural application for such devices. Memristors are being reported from a diverse class of materials including but not limited to organic semiconductors⁹, biopolymers¹⁰, halide perovskites¹¹ and metal oxides¹².

Figures of merit of memristors:

On-off ratio: The ratio of current in high resistance state (HRS) and low resistance state (LRS) and determines the memory window of the device. $\text{On-off} = \text{LRS}/\text{HRS}$ and naturally it's dimensionless⁷

Retention: The ability of device to hold memory for a duration of time thus this determines the volatility of memory. It is measured in seconds⁷

Endurance: The ability to withstand set and reset cycles without losing information.⁷

Switching Behaviour:

Interfacial behaviour as the name suggests is caused due to effects such as change in polarization, Schottky barrier, charge accumulation at the metal, active layer interface, etc.¹⁰ This behaviour can be observed with gradual resistive switching, lower on-off ratio but excellent repeatability and potentiation characteristics making it a good choice for neuromorphic computing application.

Filamentary behaviour is usually evident by abrupt resistive switching and high on-off ratio but with higher stochasticity and loop to loop variation. these devices utilize the formation of conductive filaments caused by factors such as voltage stress and joule heating within the device. These filaments can be of halide vacancies and metal electrode ion penetration in metal halide perovskite memristors. Overall due to fast speed and high memory window these devices are excellent candidates for future digital memory application.¹⁰

Figure 3 : illustration of a memristor with a top electrode (TE) and a Bottom electrode (BE) showing a) Interfacial resistive switching, b) filamentary resistive switching

Types of Hysteresis

Capacitive As the name suggests, this is the type of hysteresis caused by capacitive effects in the device and can be seen as the current going in clockwise direction with respect to voltage^{11,13}. Usually this is caused due to the ionic and electronic capacitance of the perovskite.

Inductive This is due to the inductive effects within the device and can be seen as the current going anticlockwise with respect to voltage. The origins of this kind of hysteresis could be attributed to ionic lag in perovskites but it is still a matter of debate.^{11,13}

Figure 4: Illustration of a) Capacitive hysteresis and b) inductive hysteresis

2.3. Impedance Spectroscopy

Impedance spectroscopy (IS) is a frequency domain measurement mapping the impedance of a device across various frequencies. This gives out the real and imaginary part alongside the total impedance and phase for each measured frequency. IS is a powerful probe to study charge transport, microscopic properties and material characteristics. Making IS being widely used in electrochemistry, semiconductor device physics and materials physics.¹⁴⁻¹⁶

IS data can be represented in two ways namely Bode and Nyquist, in the bode representation the Total impedance alongside Phase is on the Y axes and the frequency is on the X axis and in the Nyquist representation the imaginary component of impedance is on the Y axis and the real component on the X axis.

Using the Nyquist representation, we can find an equivalent circuit for the device by modelling an imaginary circuit with circuit elements like resistors, capacitors and inductors which closely matches the impedance of the device. This helps us comment on the capacitive and inductive effects within the device and map components such as ionic and electronic capacitance, series resistance, etc.

Figure 5: illustration of Nyquist and Bode representation of IS data¹⁵.

2.4. Neuromorphic Devices:

Recently, several optoelectronic devices have been proposed and characterised for brain inspired computing. These devices include memristors^{3,17}, field effect transistors¹⁸ and spintronic memories¹⁹ among many others. The common thing in these devices is the presence of hysteresis which is necessary for potentiation like behaviour. These devices possess the ability to be potentiated like a biological synapse and the synaptic weight is determined by the number and duration of learning cycles (epochs).

These devices can be described using:

Excitatory Post Synaptic Current (EPSC): This is the current output to the presynaptic stimulus, in our case voltage and light.

Pulse Paired Facilitation: This is the potentiation seen by giving just two presynaptic pulses and measuring the EPSC. PPF determines the short-term plasticity (STP) of the devices and can be determined using PPF index. $I_{ppf} = ((A2 - A1)/A1) * 100$. Where A2 is the peak current for second pulse and A1 is the peak current for first pulse.

Long Term Potentiation: This is the potentiation observed after exciting the device numerous times with the same pulse or one time with a very intense pulse. This indicates the long-term memory of the device.

2.5. CALM model and Potentiation

The Conductance-Activated quasi-Linear Memristor (CALM) model¹⁷ is a kinetic framework where a single state variable $X(u,t) \in [0,1]$ represents the normalized conductance between a low-conductance baseline g_L and a high-conductance plateau g_H . Using experimental values for relaxation time, g_L , g_H , we can model a memristor like¹⁷, The governing equations are:

$$(1) \quad I_{tot}(u,X) = [g_L + (g_H - g_L) \cdot X] \cdot u + C_m \cdot (du/dt)$$

$$(2) \quad dX/dt = [X_{ss}(u) - X] / \tau_k(u)$$

Here, I_{tot} includes both the memristive ionic/electronic conduction and the parasitic capacitance C_m attributed to device geometry and double-layer charging at interfaces.

Steady-State Activation

The steady-state conductance fraction $X_{ss}(u)$ follows a sigmoidal (logistic) function capturing the voltage threshold behaviour:

$$X_{ss}(u) = 1 / [1 + \exp(-(u - V_t)/V_m)]$$

where V_t is the activation threshold (~ 1.2 V) and V_m (~ 0.15 V) controls the steepness of the transition.

Voltage-Dependent Relaxation

$\tau_k(u)$ defines how rapidly X moves towards $X_{ss}(u)$. Rather than using piecewise threshold-based updates, CALM employs a smooth double-exponential form:

$$\tau_k(u) = \tau_{min} + (\tau_{max} - \tau_{min}) \cdot [\exp(-(u - V_{OFF})/V_-) + \exp((u - V_{ON})/V_+)]^{-1}$$

But due to an anomalous character in relaxation time for the perovskite memristor the following simplistic model was devised.

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(V) &= -0.01725 + 0.44271 / [1 + e^{(14.84324 \cdot (V - 0.92197))}] - 0.34968 / [1 \\ &+ e^{(2454.41 \cdot (V - 0.83905))}]. \end{aligned}$$

with τ_{min} (~ 0.002 s) as a floor value to ensure numerical stability. V_{ON} and V_{OFF} define the voltage windows where conductance change is fastest. This form captures: (i) volatile switching when $|u| < V_{OFF}$, (ii) rapid state change near V_{ON} , and (iii) memory retention when u is removed (τ_k large near zero bias).

Potentiation Dynamics

Under a train of N identical voltage pulses (width t_p , amplitude U_0), Eq. (2) predicts a staircase increase in X towards $X_{ss}(U_0)$. Because $\tau_k(U_0)$ is finite, X does not reach X_{ss} instantaneously; successive pulses push X closer to X_{ss} , producing a current potentiation similar to synaptic weight updates. If an interval longer than τ_k is present between pulses, X relaxes back towards $X_{ss}(0) \sim 0$, leading to depression or forgetting behaviour.

Model Calibration with Experimental τ data

Experimental IS provides relaxation times τ_{exp} at discrete voltages V_{data} . By fitting $\tau_k(u)$ to these data points, the CALM model parameters (V_{ON} , V_{OFF} , V_{+} , V_{-} , τ_{max}) are extracted using both IS and IV.

Simulation of Hysteresis

By numerically integrating Eq. (2), we obtain $X(u(t))$ along a triangular voltage waveform from -1 V to $+1.5\text{ V}$ and back. The total current I_{tot} (Eq. (1)) includes the Ohmic component and the capacitive component $C_m \cdot (du/dt)$.

Pulse-Train Potentiation

For a pulse train of 50 pulses (10 ms width, 20 ms period, $U_0 = 1\text{ V}$), X increases from its initial value $X_{\text{ss}}(0) = 0$ towards $X_{\text{ss}}(1\text{ V}) \approx 0.95$, following an exponential approach characterized by $\tau_k(1\text{ V})$. Figure 18 shows the applied voltage train, the resulting current response, and the extracted current at the end of each pulse, illustrating potentiation. As pulse number increases, the current asymptotes towards a steady state, where $X \approx X_{\text{ss}}(1\text{ V})$.

2.6. UV-Vis Absorption Spectra:

UV-Visible spectroscopy is among the simplest and most widely used spectroscopy techniques used in chemistry, physics, and materials science. The basic principle is to measure the absorbance, transmittance or reflectance of any sample be it in liquid or solid form. One can, in principle, get significant information from the UV-Vis spectra including optical bandgap, Urbach energy, information about allowed and forbidden transitions, etc.

Usually while measuring the absorption spectra of any sample one assumes $A+R+T = 1$ where A is absorption, R is Reflection and T is transmission. The data is denoted in arbitrary units (a.u.) and for reliable comparison between two different measurements, normalization becomes a powerful practice.

Beer-Lambert's Law: This law relates the intensity of the transmitted light to the incident light. The intensity of a light transmitted from a medium exponentially decays based on the extinction coefficient and the distance travelled by the light in said medium.

$$I = I_0 e^{-\alpha x}$$

Here, I is the intensity of the transmitted light, I_0 is the intensity of the incident light, α is the extinction coefficient of the material and x is the thickness of the sample.

Optical bandgap: Optical bandgap is the minimum energy needed for an electronic transition in a material (energy gap between valance and conduction band/ HOMO and LUMO). It can be determined using the Tauc plot²⁰ where $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ is plotted against energy for direct band gap materials and energy at the band edge is extrapolated and $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ is plotted for indirect band gap materials.

2.7. Photoluminescence Spectra:

Photoluminescence spectroscopy (PL) tells us about the exciton dynamics of a material by measuring the light emitted from the material at a specific monochromatic excitation,

Photoluminescence can be divided into two subparts namely fluorescence and phosphorescence. Fluorescence is the instantaneous emission of light due to the generation of singlet excitons for which the excited state has the same angular momentum as the ground state. Phosphorescence is delayed emission caused by generation of triplet excitons as triplet excitons need to lose extra angular momentum via phononic relaxation thus delaying the emission^{21,22}. The energy difference between the excitation and emission is called Stokes shift²² and tells us about the loss of energy in this process. This process can be visualized easily using the Jablonski diagram, first described by Aleksander Jablonski around 1935 to describe such photophysical processes in molecules but the same principle can also be applied to solid state materials like Halide perovskites.

Figure 6: The Jablonski diagram of excitonic transitions. The energies of singlet (S₀ and S₁) and triplet (T₁ and T_n) states are scaled vertically. Absorption (1), fluorescence (2), Phononic relaxation (4), phosphorescence (6), nonradiative transitions (3 and 5) and photo induced absorption (7)²¹

3. Methodology / project development

The methods used for this work can be broadly divided into three divisions namely device fabrication, electrical characterization and modelling.

3.1. Device Fabrication:

The halide perovskite memristor with the architecture (FTO|PEDOT: PSS|MAPbBr₃|Au) was fabricated by first partially etching the FTO substrates using Zn powder and dilute HCL (2M), the substrates were subsequently cleaned with detergent, DI water, Acetone and IPA via ultrasonication for 15 minutes each and finally were treated via UV-Ozone for 30 minutes for improved surface wettability and slightly increased work-function.

PEDOT: PSS (AI 4083) solution was filtered with 0.45µm µm PTFE filter and spin-coated for 30s at 3000RPM and annealed at 150°C for 15 mins.

The 1.4M MAPbBr₃ precursor was prepared by dissolving MABr and PbBr₂ in DMF and DMSO blend of ratio 1:4 using a magnetic stirrer at room temperature. This precursor was spin-coated via a two-step process with first at 1000RPM at 10s to spread the material and second at 4000RPM at 40s for appropriate thickness and uniformity. Toluene was used as an antisolvent 100µL of which was dropped 20s after starting the spin coating process.

Finally, 85nm gold was thermally deposited under high vacuum (base pressure 5×10^{-7}) with the final vacuum chamber temperature of around 70°C.

Figure 7: Illustration of the fabrication procedure of MAPbBr₃ based memristors.

3.2. Electrical Characterisation:

All electrical characterizations, including current – voltage (IV), Impedance spectroscopy (IS) and chronoamperometry (CA) measurements were performed using an Autolab PGSTAT204 electrochemical workstation equipped with an FRA32M impedance module.

The I-V measurements were done by measuring current while supplying a voltage staircase ramp to the device at different scan rates (0.5V/s, 1V/s, 2V/s and 5V/s), the impedance spectra was obtained using the FRA attachment to the Autolab from 100KHz to 100mHz

with 5 points per decade, with a small AC signal amplitude of 0.01V and a constant DC bias.

The light stimulated studies were done using the Autolab LED driver kit equipped with green LED with primary wavelength 530nm. The LED source and the memristor devices were placed 20cm away from each other and three different intensities of light were illuminated by controlling the current provided to the LED at 0, 50mA, 75mA and 100mA.

Figure 8: The experimental setup to measure electrical characteristics under light and dark conditions (image ref for the equipment: metrohm.com)

3.3. Optical spectra:

UV-Vis Absorption Spectroscopy: The absorption spectra were measured using Agilent Technologies Cart 60 UV-Vis. The wavelength range of 400-800nm was scanned at a speed of 400nm per minute and a resolution of 1nm. The baseline correction was done for precleaned FTO coated glass and further the spectra were measured for PEDOT:PSS and MAPbBr₃ films.

Photoluminescence Spectroscopy: The emission spectra were measured using Edinburgh instruments FLS 1000 with an excitation wavelength of 405nm and at a range from 450nm to 800nm for both PEDOT:PSS and the whole device stack. The bandwidth was fixed at 10nm.

3.4. Device Modelling:

The IS data was modelled using the RelaxIS software to obtain the internal parameters of the device such as relaxation time, internal resistances, ionic and electronic capacitance. The I-V was analysed using excel to find out g_L , g_H , threshold voltage and slope of activation. Finally, all this information was used in accordance with the CALM framework using a custom code on Python employing the 'Numpy' and 'matplotlib' libraries for numerical calculations and plotting respectively. The said code can be found in the appendix. The voltage dependence of relaxation time τ_K (V) was modelled with the help of Wolfram alpha.

4. Results

4.1. I-V characteristics:

Figure 9a presents DC I-V hysteresis loops for a representative device under dark conditions at scan rates of 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 5.0 and 10.0 V s^{-1} . It is evident from the fact that there is a change from clockwise hysteresis (Capacitive) to anticlockwise hysteresis (Inductive) at around 0.8V. This inductive hysteresis also increases with lower scan rate and is only present in scan rates lower than about 2V s^{-1} , whereby its very minimal and grows significantly for 1V s^{-1} , which indicates that the inductance could be attributed to ionic lag. This is because, in principle, higher scan rate should increase inductance but here instead of just electronic transport, ions also get involved at lower scan rates, but the rate is not slow enough to polarize the ions completely thus giving a “lag” and causing inductance. The devices show excellent loop to loop reproducibility, showing minimal change in hysteresis with each cycle.

Figure 9: IV characteristics of FTO/PEDOT:PSS/MAPbBr₃/Au memristors in both semi-log and linear scales with a) different scan rates, b) different voltage bias, and c) Loop to Loop variation.

The devices show gradual switching with an on-off ratio of about 20 and retention of more than 150 Cycles, indicating that interfacial switching is the dominant mechanism, which can also be attributed to the use of gold for top electrode, being electrochemically inactive, doesn't cause ion penetration into the perovskite which is required for filamentary switching.

Figure 10: the endurance of the MAPbBr₃ memristor

The endurance was measured with a pulse train of read, set, read, reset, read with set voltage being 1.4V, read voltage being 0.3V and reset voltage being 0.1V.

4.2. Impedance spectra

Impedance Spectroscopy (IS) Nyquist plots, from -0.6 V to $+1.0\text{ V}$, are displayed in the figure 11 (a) and (b) for negative and positive voltage bias, respectively. From the plots, one can see, that for most of the voltages, the device exhibits a two semicircle like behaviour in the first quadrant, which indicates two separate capacitors in parallel. From -0.6 V to a 0.6 V the negative imaginary part of impedance is always positive which indicates a predominantly capacitive behaviour, be it with reduction in the capacitance of the second capacitor. But, when the bias reaches 0.7 volts , the negative imaginary part starts becoming negative exhibiting inductive behaviour at lower frequencies, this is also consistent with the I-V characteristics where we start seeing the inductive hysteresis above 0.7 V at lower scan rates. We also see the overall impedance reducing because of higher current values.

Figure 11: Nyquist plots for IS data a) for negative voltages, and b) for positive voltage

4.3. IS modelling and equivalent circuit

The equivalent circuit in the figure 12(a) was used to fit the impedance data, at lower voltages, until the capacitive to inductive transition, Ca gives the capacitive effect and at voltages after 0.7V, L gives the inductive effect.

Figure 12: a) illustration of the equivalent circuit used to model IS, b) Fitted IS data for positive voltages, c) Fitted IS data for negative voltages

Voltage (V)	TauC (ms)	TauL (ms)	C0 (C)	Ca (C)	L (kH)	Ra (Ω)	Rb (Ω)	RL (Ω)
-0.6	3.218E-02	-	5.660E-08	1.669E-05	-	1.816E+03	3.655E+04	3.607E-03
-0.4	3.689E-02	-	4.808E-08	1.527E-05	-	2.168E+03	5.377E+04	1.209E+04
-0.2	4.513E-02	-	4.204E-08	1.634E-05	-	2.408E+03	7.122E+10	1.864E+04
0	5.602E-02	-	4.591E-08	7.186E-06	-	5.491E+03	9.428E+11	2.193E+04
0.1	6.068E-02	-	4.603E-08	7.756E-06	-	5.501E+03	6.690E+14	2.130E+04
0.2	6.749E-02	-	4.626E-08	8.581E-06	-	5.390E+03	2.138E+11	1.997E+04
0.3	6.991E-02	-	4.652E-08	8.557E-06	-	5.341E+03	1.222E+11	1.309E+04
0.4	6.211E-02	-	4.635E-08	7.236E-06	-	5.235E+03	1.097E+11	1.709E+04

0.5	5.048E-02	-	4.513E-08	5.721E-06	-	5.099E+03	1.087E+11	1.287E+04
0.6	3.226E-02	-	4.410E-08	3.071E-06	-	9.563E+03	1.094E+04	2.572E-03
0.7	3.505E-02	1.537E-01	3.949E-08	6.335E-06	1.550E+03	6.514E+03	1.762E+04	8.908E+03
0.8	4.300E-03	1.437E-01	3.750E-08	3.730E-07	9.640E+02	1.154E+04	6.432E+03	6.706E+03
0.9	6.593E-04	9.828E-02	3.506E-08	6.934E-08	2.400E+02	9.508E+03	4.895E+03	2.444E+03
1	1.632E-06	5.934E-02	1.585E-08	1.565E-09	6.770E+01	8.586E+02	3.017E+03	1.141E+03

Table 1: Parameters extracted from impedance modelling

Ca is about 2 orders of magnitude higher than Cb which indicates that Ca is the double layer ionic capacitance and Cb is the electronic capacitance. Due to their nature, Ca is independent of the perovskite thickness, but Cb can change as an inverse to thickness.

Figure 13: IS parameters with respect to voltage bias, a) Relaxation time, b) conductance, c) inductance, d) I-V characteristics (not from impedance) e) ionic capacitance, f) electronic capacitance.

As for the relaxation time, we can see that relaxation time related to the capacitance takes a peak at about 0.3 and follows a gaussian like curve across the board, since the inductor does not appear before the transition voltage, we only get a few points for the value of relaxation time related to the inductance with respect to voltage, making it difficult to create a function for the same to apply in CALM.

4.4. Pulse train potentiation

The pulse train experiment included measuring the current response to two different voltage square pulse trains, one with period 20ms and another with period 400ms, both with a variety of voltage amplitudes. The pulse train with 20ms period (figure 14 (a) and (b)) show effective inductive rise after about 1V and thus also shows potentiation at that voltage as can be seen in the graphs with complete time scale. The pulse train with period 400ms shows the inductive rise at much lower voltages (about 0.6V), interestingly we also see a capacitive fall after the inductive rise after about 80ms in each pulse, which indicates that the ionic capacitance starts contributing to the transient current at that point. We see a similar potentiation at this pulse train as well.

Figure 14: pulse train characteristics a) different voltages amplitudes with period of 20ms from showing 5 pulses, b) full output of the 20ms pulses, c) 400ms time period, showing three pulses, d) full output for the 400ms time period pulses.

4.5. **Light stimulation:**

The current levels increase significantly in the right side of the I-V curves for the lowest intensity and start to saturate for higher intensities of light, as can be observed more easily in the semi-log representation of I-V. Another interesting observation is that the inductive hysteresis is suppressed to low levels and the transition from capacitive to inductive behaviour goes from about 0.7V in dark to about 1.4 in the lowest light intensity and for higher intensities the hysteresis is completely capacitive. This can also be seen at the IS taken at 0V for different light intensities, even though the impedance is overall lower due to higher current, the second capacitor is increasing with light intensity, especially when compared to the first capacitor. Another interesting thing to note is at 1V the impedance is still largely inductive, and thus, light stimulation can be used to potentiate these devices.

Figure 15 a) I-V characteristics with different light intensities in linear scale, b) in semi-log scale, c) IS at 0V with different light intensities and b) at IS at 1V with different light intensities

In the figure 16, one can see that we have successfully potentiated the memristors with light stimulation, here the input pulse of two pulses, three pulses and four pulses were taken together to observe a clear “learning” effect. In figure 16(a) and (b) the first part can be taken as pulse paired facilitation (PPF) which is one of the most basic characteristics of potentiation and gives insights into the short-term plasticity^{3,7}. In all these figures, it is also

worthy to note that the first impulse response is more capacitive and consecutive responses are increasingly inductive in nature. This inductive rise is essential for potentiation. In figure 16 (c), as a result of 9 pulses, the system is potentiated enough that it takes about 5 seconds to depress which is significant for a non-volatile memristor, giving a long-term plasticity effect in some sense. Interestingly, light stimulation for longer time gives a higher PPF index (learning rate) for the stimulus of longer duration, that's why we used the 0.5s pulses for the LTP experiment.

Figure 16: 100mA Light stimulated potentiation a) with 0.2s light pulses and 5 s breaks, b) with 0.5s light pulses and 5s breaks, c) 9 consecutive 0.5s light pulses, d) input pulse illustration for (a) and (b), e) input pulse illustration for (c)

	0.2s 100mA green LED	0.5s 100mA green LED
PPF Index	28%	52%

Table 2: PPF Index under light stimulation

4.6. Calm model validation:

Using the extracted parameters ($V_t = 1.2$ V, $V_m = 0.15$ V, $\tau_{min} = 0.002$ s, $\tau_{max} = 0.5$ s, $V_{ON} = 0.85$ V, $V_{OFF} = 0.3$ V, $V_+ = 0.05$ V, $V_- = 0.07$ V), the CALM model is validated against experimental data. As we can see the I-V curves simulated show some similarities to the experimental curves such as the capacitive to inductive transition at about 0.7V due to the relaxation time disappearing there but does not show complete agreement with the experimental data, in general.

Figure 17: a) experimental relaxation time overlaid on the mathematical model, b) steady state activation function, c) state variable – voltage, d) state variable – time, e) I-V characteristics in linear scale and d) in semi-log scale

The potentiation curves achieved using the code show good agreement with the experimental data, as both start showing saturation after about 20 pulses and show the inductive rise effectively.

Figure 18: a) Voltage pulse input for CALM simulation, b) current output as a function of time, c) current output as a function of pulse number

Although the simplicity of the model, makes it unfeasible to be used for simulating I-V characteristics, thus a more complex and accurate model needs to be devised for simulating Halide perovskite memristors precisely. This is supposed to be the continuation

of this work and is outside the scope of a two-month project and by extension, this master's thesis.

4.7. Optical Spectra

The absorption spectra, of the perovskite thin film (figure 19a), matches quite well with literature showing an absorption peak around 530nm. The Tauc plots (figure 19c) suggest that the optical band gap is around 2.3eV thus light sources with higher energy than that can only be used. With the fluorescence spectra (figure 19c), we can see that the emission is remarkably close to the absorption peak.

In figure 19b, we can see three different emission spectra, one of the device from the front (perovskite) side, where we see just a single strong emission around 545nm, one of a single PEDOT: PSS thin film which shows a more wide emission across the spectra with the peak at about 715nm and one measured from the back (Glass side) of the device where the emission is a combination of both MAPbBr₃ and PEDOT:PSS. This is due to the higher thickness of perovskite when compared to PEDOT:PSS as when the emission was measured from the front (perovskite first) side, the monochromatic light can only enter the perovskite and thus the relevant emission is observed, whereas when emission is measured from the back side (glass first), the PEDOT:PSS (about 30nm thin) allows light to pass through and reach the perovskite, thus allowing us to observe an emission for both.

To find out the Stokes shift we, find out the difference in the wavelength of absorption peak and emission peak, and calculate the corresponding energy using the nifty shorthand, $\Delta E = 1240/\Delta\lambda$. Here ΔE is the Stoke shift in electron volts and $\Delta\lambda$ is the wavelength difference in nanometres. This comes out to be about 130meV which is not very high but significant enough (>100meV) to suggest the presence of lattice defects like Br vacancies.

Overall keeping the optical bandgap, absorption and emission in mind, the 530nm Wavelength LED from metrohm was selected as our source for the light stimulated experiments.

Figure 19: a) UV-Vis absorption spectra of MAPbBr₃ thin films, b) The emission spectra of the device stack from front, back side and of a PEDOT: PSS thin film, c) Tauc Plots for the MAPbBr₃ thin films

5. Discussion

This investigation characterizes halide perovskite-based memristors with architecture (FTO | PEDOT:PSS | MAPbBr₃ | Au). Employing , I–V hysteresis, impedance spectroscopy (IS), pulse-train potentiation, and optical stimulation, we successfully observe the rich interplay of ionic and electronic dynamics in these devices.

A key observation was the distinct transition from capacitive to inductive hysteresis around 0.7 V, prominently at intermediate scan rates. This transition points towards an ionic lag, supported by IS data revealing inductive loops at higher voltages. The capacitance was also attributed to both ionic double layer capacitance and electronic capacitance which was observed with the pulse train potentiation experiment at longer time scales.

The presence of two different relaxation times, one for the capacitor (τ_c) and another for the inductor (τ_L), this is reported earlier for perovskite solar cells, but this is the first time such phenomenon has been observed in a memristor. One key difference with the solar cell reports is that, both capacitive and inductive relaxation times are the same before diverging alongside the fact that in the solar cell the relaxation times are pretty much constant with voltage before and after diverging²³. Whereas in our observation with the memristor both relaxation times follow a gaussian like dependence with voltage.

The Conductance-Activated quasi-Linear Memristor (CALM) model provided a foundational approach for device simulation but fell short of accurately depicting the I-V characteristics observed experimentally. The simplified mathematical representation was insufficient to replicate the ionic-electronic interplay, highlighting a critical need for developing more mathematically rigorous computational models specifically tailored to halide perovskite memristors. And this failure could be attributed to the presence of two different relaxation times unlike the previous reports with nanofluidic memristor which presents a single relaxation time¹⁷ and the ionic capacitance at lower frequencies.

To model these memristors with the experimental data, one needs to use coupled differential equations where one equation is used to describe each of the relaxation times and then the current should be described by an equation employing the solutions to both the coupled equations and an additional low frequency capacitive component.

Impedance spectroscopy helped us comment on the underlying processes, revealing two distinct capacitive behaviours linked to ionic and electronic domains within the device. The fitted equivalent circuit parameters reinforced the complexity of ionic-electronic interactions, with a clear dominance of ionic capacitance at lower frequencies, reinforcing the need for detailed impedance modelling.

Neuromorphic characteristics, explored via pulse-train experiments, indicated significant potentiation, showcasing the memristor's potential in emulating neuronal synaptic behaviour. Especially, the observed pulse-pair facilitation (PPF) showing excellent short-term memory due to the device's volatility and extended potentiation (spike number dependent plasticity) proved the device's applicability in neuromorphic applications. Additionally, introducing optical stimuli showed significant change in device characteristics including shift in the capacitive to inductive transition and presence of excellent potentiation behaviour under light stimulation.

Optical characterization showed the suitability of MAPbBr_3 for optoelectronic applications, with minimal Stokes shift signifying efficient exciton dynamics and less loss. This finding reinforces the material's potential utility in neuromorphic computing.

6. Budget

- FTO coated glasses x 60 = 360 Euros
- PEDOT: PSS x 12mL = 31.8 Euros
- MABr x 0.7g = 22.52 Euros
- PbBr_2 x 5g = 72 Euros
- Gold x 1g = 93 Euros
- Solvents =50 euros

7. Environment Impact

The halide perovskite used for this study possesses lead, which is toxic and, Gold and FTO substrates used in this study can't be recycled easily, thus appropriate safety and disposal measures were taken during the experimentation. This study provides important insights into the working principles of Halide perovskite devices which has a huge positive impact in areas such as solar energy and neuromorphic computing, former contributes massively to green and sustainable energy and latter has the potential to reduce energy consumption of our computing needs significantly. Thus, overall, project has had a positive environmental impact.

8. Conclusions and future development

Several batches of MAPbBr₃ memristors were fabricated and characterised, the devices showed excellent cycle to cycle and device to device reproducibility, on off ratio of over 20 and endurance greater than 150 cycles. I-V and IS were employed to comment on the nature of hysteresis and find the origin of this change of behaviour. IS data was fitted to obtain the parameters of the devices and use the same for CALM model. Pulse train characteristics were obtained both experimentally and computationally and were used to comment on potential neuromorphic applications and charge transport properties of these devices. The CALM model using a custom-made python code was found a bit too simplistic for halide perovskite memristors due to the presence of low frequency capacitive effects and possible improvements to the model were suggested. The devices were potentiated with both light and voltage stimulus suggesting good suitability of halide perovskite memristor for neuromorphic computing.

Future development plan is to formulate a more complex and detailed model to simulate these memristors more precisely and to do more light dependent studies for neuromorphic computing applications. One interesting study which could be done is to try and find an equivalence between optical and electrical stimulus, i.e. the specific conditions whereby the response to both kind of stimulus is similar. Overall, we plan to refine these findings and publish these results as relevant journal articles.

Bibliography

- (1) Wulf, Wm. A.; McKee, S. A. Hitting the Memory Wall: Implications of the Obvious. *ACM SIGARCH Comput. Archit. News* **1995**, *23* (1), 20–24. <https://doi.org/10.1145/216585.216588>.
- (2) Mead, C. Neuromorphic Electronic Systems. *Proc. IEEE* **1990**, *78* (10), 1629–1636. <https://doi.org/10.1109/5.58356>.
- (3) Cui, D.; Pei, M.; Lin, Z.; Zhang, H.; Kang, M.; Wang, Y.; Gao, X.; Su, J.; Miao, J.; Li, Y.; Zhang, J.; Hao, Y.; Chang, J. Versatile Optoelectronic Memristor Based on Wide-Bandgap Ga₂O₃ for Artificial Synapses and Neuromorphic Computing. *Light Sci. Appl.* **2025**, *14* (1), 161. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41377-025-01773-6>.
- (4) Jiang, B.; Chen, X.; Pan, X.; Tao, L.; Huang, Y.; Tang, J.; Li, X.; Wang, P.; Ma, G.; Zhang, J.; Wang, H. Advances in Metal Halide Perovskite Memristors: A Review from a Co-Design Perspective. *Adv. Sci.* **2025**, *12* (2), 2409291. <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.202409291>.
- (5) Noman, M.; Khan, Z.; Jan, S. T. A Comprehensive Review on the Advancements and Challenges in Perovskite Solar Cell Technology. *RSC Adv.* **2024**, *14* (8), 5085–5131. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3RA07518D>.
- (6) Eames, C.; Frost, J. M.; Barnes, P. R. F.; O'Regan, B. C.; Walsh, A.; Islam, M. S. Ionic Transport in Hybrid Lead Iodide Perovskite Solar Cells. *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, *6* (1), 7497. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms8497>.
- (7) Kim, S.-Y.; Zhang, H.; Rubio-Magnieto, J. Operating Mechanism Principles and Advancements for Halide Perovskite-Based Memristors and Neuromorphic Devices. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2024**, *15* (40), 10087–10103. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.4c02170>.
- (8) Chua, L. Memristor-The Missing Circuit Element. *IEEE Trans. Circuit Theory* **1971**, *18* (5), 507–519. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCT.1971.1083337>.
- (9) Wang, X.; Li, W.; Zhao, J.; Wang, F.; Fan, L.; Chen, Z.; Wang, P.; Zhai, Y.; Gao, Z.; Qu, W.; Wang, H.; Wei, B. Digital Organic Memristor Based on P3HT Doped with Organic Small Molecules TmPyPB/ TpPyPB. *Org. Electron.* **2025**, *144*, 107281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orgel.2025.107281>.
- (10) Kiran, M. R.; Yadav, Y.; Singh, S. P. Chitosan Based Memory Devices: Filamentary versus Interfacial Resistive Switching. *J. Phys. Appl. Phys.* **2022**, *55* (5), 055302. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/ac2fd9>.
- (11) Gonzales, C.; Bou, A.; Guerrero, A.; Bisquert, J. Capacitive and Inductive Characteristics of Volatile Perovskite Resistive Switching Devices with Analog Memory. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2024**, *15* (25), 6496–6503. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.4c00945>.
- (12) Patil, A. R.; Dongale, T. D.; Kamat, R. K.; Rajpure, K. Y. Binary Metal Oxide-Based Resistive Switching Memory Devices: A Status Review. *Mater. Today Commun.* **2023**, *34*, 105356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2023.105356>.
- (13) Bisquert, J. Inductive and Capacitive Hysteresis of Current-Voltage Curves: Unified Structural Dynamics in Solar Energy Devices, Memristors, Ionic Transistors, and Bioelectronics. *PRX Energy* **2024**, *3* (1), 011001. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PRXEnergy.3.011001>.
- (14) *Impedance Spectroscopy: Theory, Experiment, and Applications*, Third edition.; Barsoukov, E., Macdonald, J. R., Eds.; Wiley: Hoboken, NJ, 2018.

- (15) Choi, W.; Shin, H.-C.; Kim, J. M.; Choi, J.-Y.; Yoon, W.-S. Modeling and Applications of Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) for Lithium-Ion Batteries. *J. Electrochem. Sci. Technol.* **2020**, *11* (1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.33961/jecst.2019.00528>.
- (16) Yadav, D.; Gora, S.; Kumar, A.; Jangra, M.; Yadav, K. L.; Datta, A.; Bag, M. Probing the Photo-Activated Switching Dynamics of Halide Perovskite Memristors. *ACS Appl. Electron. Mater.* **2023**, *5* (7), 3765–3771. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaelm.3c00483>.
- (17) Rivera-Sierra, G.; Ramirez, P.; Bisquert, J.; Bou, A. Relaxation Time of Multipore Nanofluidic Memristors for Neuromorphic Applications. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2025**, *147* (20), 17529–17538. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.5c04903>.
- (18) Mandal, B.; Sonar, P.; Singh, S. P. Visible Light-Stimulated Artificial Synapse Based on an Organic Field-Effect Transistor for Imitating Human Emotions and Mood Swings. *ACS Appl. Electron. Mater.* **2024**, *6* (4), 2420–2433. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaelm.4c00079>.
- (19) Marrows, C. H.; Barker, J.; Moore, T. A.; Moorsom, T. Neuromorphic Computing with Spintronics. *Npj Spintron.* **2024**, *2* (1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44306-024-00019-2>.
- (20) Tauc, J. Absorption Edge and Internal Electric Fields in Amorphous Semiconductors. *Mater. Res. Bull.* **1970**, *5* (8), 721–729. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-5408\(70\)90112-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-5408(70)90112-1).
- (21) Mikhnenko, O. V.; Blom, P. W. M.; Nguyen, T.-Q. Exciton Diffusion in Organic Semiconductors. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2015**, *8* (7), 1867–1888. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5EE00925A>.
- (22) Lakowicz, J. R.; Masters, B. R. Principles of Fluorescence Spectroscopy, Third Edition. *J. Biomed. Opt.* **2008**, *13* (2), 029901. <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.2904580>.
- (23) H. Balaguera, E.; Bisquert, J. Mapping of Internal Ionic/Electronic Transient Dynamics in Current–Voltage Operation of Perovskite Solar Cells. *Small* **2025**, *21* (2), 2409534. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.202409534>.

Appendix

A1: Python Code

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# =====
# Model Parameters
# =====
Cm = 1e-9    # Capacitance [F]
gL = 1e-6    # Low-state conductance [S]
gH = 1e-3    # High-state conductance [S]
Vt = 1.2     # Steady-state threshold [V]
Vm = 0.15    # Steepness for X_ss [V]
tau_floor = 0.002 # Minimum  $\tau_X$  [s]

# =====
# Lookup - table functions
# =====
def x_ss(u):
    """Steady-state activation."""
    return 1 / (1 + np.exp(-(u - Vt) / Vm))

def tau_x(u):
    """Voltage - dependent time constant with a floor to smooth discontinuities."""
    # Clip argument range to avoid overflow
    a1 = np.clip((0.06741**-1) * (u - 0.92197), -100, 100)
    a2 = np.clip((0.00393**-1) * (u - 0.83905), -100, 100)
    base = (
        -0.01725
        + 0.44271 / (1 + np.exp(a1))
        - 0.34968 / (1 + np.exp(a2))
    )
    return np.clip(base, tau_floor, None)
```

```
# Experimental τ data
V_data = np.array([-0.7, -0.5, -0.3, -0.1, 0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4,
                  0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1.0])
tau_data = np.array([5.01e-2, 5.77e-2, 6.65e-2, 8.17e-2, 8.67e-2, 8.16e-2,
                    8.10e-2, 8.17e-2, 8.32e-2, 8.24e-2, 7.67e-2, 6.13e-2,
                    1.08e-2, 2.41e-1, 8.83e-2])

# =====
# Precompute common arrays
# =====
vmin, vmax = -1.0, 1.5
u_plot = np.linspace(vmin, vmax, 500)

# =====
# I-V Hysteresis Simulation
# =====
rate = 1.0 # V/s
dt_iv = 1e-3 # s
t_leg = (vmax - vmin) / rate
t_f = np.arange(0, t_leg, dt_iv)
t_r = np.arange(0, t_leg, dt_iv)
u_iv = np.concatenate((vmin + rate*t_f, vmax - rate*t_r))
du_iv = np.gradient(u_iv, dt_iv)
t_iv = np.concatenate((t_f, t_leg + t_r))

x_iv = np.zeros_like(u_iv)
x_iv[0] = x_ss(u_iv[0])
for i in range(1, len(u_iv)):
    x_iv[i] = x_iv[i-1] + (x_ss(u_iv[i-1]) - x_iv[i-1]) / tau_x(u_iv[i-1]) * dt_iv

I_iv = (gL + (gH - gL) * x_iv) * u_iv + Cm * du_iv

# =====
```

```

# Pulse - Train Potentiation
# =====
num_pulses = 50
pulse_width = 10e-3 # s
period = 20e-3 # s
U0 = 1 # V
dt_pt = 1e-4 # s
t_total = num_pulses * period
t_pt = np.arange(0, t_total, dt_pt)

u_pt = np.zeros_like(t_pt)
pulse_ends = []
for n in range(num_pulses):
    start = int(n * period / dt_pt)
    end = int((n * period + pulse_width) / dt_pt)
    u_pt[start:end] = U0
    pulse_ends.append(end - 1)

x_pt = np.zeros_like(t_pt)
x_pt[0] = x_ss(0)
l_pt = np.zeros_like(t_pt)
for i in range(1, len(t_pt)):
    x_pt[i] = x_pt[i-1] + (x_ss(u_pt[i-1]) - x_pt[i-1]) / tau_x(u_pt[i-1]) * dt_pt
    du_dt = (u_pt[i] - u_pt[i-1]) / dt_pt
    l_pt[i] = (gL + (gH - gL) * x_pt[i]) * u_pt[i] + Cm * du_dt

l_pulse = [l_pt[idx] for idx in pulse_ends]

# =====
# Plotting all results
# =====
# Figure 1:  $\tau_X$  and  $X_{ss}$ ,  $x$  vs  $V/t$ , IV linear & semilog
plt.figure(figsize=(14, 12))

```

```
plt.subplot(3, 2, 1)
plt.plot(u_plot, tau_x(u_plot)*1e3, label='Model  $\tau_X(u)$ ', linewidth=2)
plt.scatter(V_data, tau_data*1e3, color='red', label='Experimental', zorder=5)
plt.xlabel('Voltage (V)'); plt.ylabel('τ_X (ms)')
plt.title('Time Constant  $\tau_X(u)$ '); plt.legend(); plt.grid(True)
```

```
plt.subplot(3, 2, 2)
plt.plot(u_plot, x_ss(u_plot), linewidth=2)
plt.xlabel('Voltage (V)'); plt.ylabel('X_ss(u)')
plt.title('Steady-State Activation'); plt.grid(True)
```

```
plt.subplot(3, 2, 3)
plt.plot(u_iv, x_iv, linewidth=2)
plt.xlabel('Voltage (V)'); plt.ylabel('x')
plt.title('State Variable vs Voltage'); plt.grid(True)
```

```
plt.subplot(3, 2, 4)
plt.plot(t_iv, x_iv, linewidth=2)
plt.xlabel('Time (s)'); plt.ylabel('x')
plt.title('State Variable vs Time'); plt.grid(True)
```

```
plt.subplot(3, 2, 5)
plt.plot(u_iv, I_iv, linewidth=2)
plt.xlabel('Voltage (V)'); plt.ylabel('Current (A)')
plt.title('I–V Hysteresis (Linear)'); plt.grid(True)
```

```
plt.subplot(3, 2, 6)
plt.semilogy(u_iv, np.abs(I_iv), linewidth=2)
plt.xlabel('Voltage (V)'); plt.ylabel('|I| (A)')
plt.title('I–V Hysteresis (Semilog)')
plt.grid(True, which='both', linestyle='--', linewidth=0.5)
```

```
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

```
# Figure 2: Pulse train, current vs time, and potentiation vs pulse number
```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 8))
```

```
plt.subplot(3, 1, 1)
```

```
plt.plot(t_pt*1e3, u_pt, color='tab:blue')
```

```
plt.ylabel('Voltage (V)')
```

```
plt.title('Pulse Train & Response')
```

```
plt.grid(True)
```

```
plt.subplot(3, 1, 2)
```

```
plt.plot(t_pt*1e3, I_pt, color='tab:green')
```

```
plt.ylabel('Current (A)')
```

```
plt.title('Current vs Time')
```

```
plt.grid(True)
```

```
plt.subplot(3, 1, 3)
```

```
plt.plot(np.arange(1, num_pulses+1), I_pulse, marker='o', linestyle='-',  
         color='tab:orange')
```

```
plt.xlabel('Pulse Number'); plt.ylabel('Current (A)')
```

```
plt.grid(True)
```

```
plt.tight_layout()
```

```
plt.show()
```

Glossary

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CALM	Conductance-Activated quasi-Linear Memristor
CA	Chronoamperometry
DC	Direct-Current (e.g., <i>DC I–V</i> loops)
DMF	*N, N-*Dimethylformamide (solvent)
DMSO	Dimethyl-sulfoxide (solvent)
IS	Impedance Spectroscopy
FTO	Fluorine-doped Tin Oxide (substrate)
HRS	High-Resistance State
IPA	Iso-propyl alcohol (solvent)
I–V	Current–Voltage (characteristic)
LED	Light-Emitting Diode
LRS	Low-Resistance State
MABr	Methyl-ammonium Bromide (precursor salt)
MAPbBr₃	Methyl-ammonium Lead Bromide (perovskite)
MIEC	Mixed Ionic–Electronic Conductor
PEDOT: PSS	Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene): poly(styrene-sulfonate)
PL	Photoluminescence
PPF	Paired-Pulse Facilitation
RPM	Revolutions Per Minute (spin-coating speed)
UV-Vis	Ultraviolet–Visible (spectroscopy)

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